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Factors that affect university bioorganic chemistry study of "Medicine" faculty 2nd year students, which graduated from Medical College

*Antypenko L. M., PhD, Assistant Professor,
Kovalenko S. I., Dr., Professor, Head of
Organic and Bioorganic Chemistry Department,
Zaporizhzhya State Medical University*

Abstract. In order to optimize the Bioorganic Chemistry studying of the Medical Faculty second year students of Zaporizhzhya State Medical University, graduated from Medical College, the relationship between some parameters of university learning: the preparation time for the theoretical part of the lesson, for computer testing and its results, the influence of the school basic knowledge at the Bioorganic Chemistry study, and in general for all disciplines, with the help of Pearson, Spearman correlations, and Kolmogorov-Smirnov comparison.

Key words: organic and bioorganic chemistry, university education, Pearson product moment correlation, Spearman rank correlation, Kolmogorov-Smirnov test.

The students that already obtained bachelor degree as Medical assistants (specialty "Medicine"), Nurses ("Nursing") and Midwives ("Obstetrics"), when entering the second year of university education, have to complete the academic difference. Bioorganic chemistry is one of such very important, but missing subjects. The main problem of their teaching is a large interval between school graduation and university studies as well as very intense material, which leads to significant problems in the assimilation of the material.

In order to detect the most significant levers of influence to improve the quality of education the Pearson product moment correlation [1], Kolmogorov-Smirnov test [2] and Spearman rank correlation [3] were calculated for Bioorganic Chemistry studying of the Medical Faculty second year students of Zaporizhzhya State Medical University, graduated from Medical College, namely, the relationship between some parameters

of university learning: the preparation time for the theoretical part of the lesson, for computer testing and its results, the influence of the school basic knowledge at the Bioorganic Chemistry study, and in general for all disciplines.

As expected, according to the Pearson correlation results, the higher students had school certificate rating and the better they passed the computer tests – the better they had bioorganic chemistry mark. So, having organic chemistry at school was essential to enter the university (Table1).

Table 1.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation data

$$r = \frac{N \sum (X - M_X) * (Y - M_Y)}{\sqrt{(\sum (X - M_X)^2 * \sum (Y - M_Y)^2)}}$$

Parameters	A*	B	C	D	E	F
A*	1					
B	-0,41347	1				
C	0,105208	-0,04263	1			
D	-0,27113	0,640347	0,179728	1		
E	-0,36894	0,321357	0,351891	0,562355	1	
F	0,088059	0,540144	0,125997	0,347632	0,120563	1

*A - average time spent for preparation for the computer test in minutes;

B - average test result in percentage;

C - average time spent for preparation for the theoretical material in minutes;

D - average bioorganic chemistry mark;

E- organic chemistry mark in school certificate;

F - average attestation mark for all studied subjects at the moment.

Also the average attestation grades were in a good correlation with tests results. Considering time, which was spent for preparation for the computer tests and their results, there was a negative relationship, meaning that students do not understand the principle of selecting the correct answer. So, more time should be dedicated for theory explanations during classes.

Verifying the type of distribution by Kolmogorov-Smirnov comparison it was detected that it was non-parametric [2]. Thus, Spearman correlation was also conducted [3].

Two correlations appeared to be statistically significant: preparation time for tests influencing their results and connection of the tests results with university bioorganic chemistry mark (Table 2).

Table 2.

Spearman correlation data

$$r_s = 1 - \frac{6 \sum d^2}{n(n^2 - 1)} \quad n=21$$

Correlations between Values	Preparation time for tests / tests results	Tests results / university bioorg. chemistry mark
Correlation coefficient	-0.53632436308701	0.55650007883099
Tf, recalculation K for critical values of Student's t-test	2.7698466711412	2.9195820418682
Critical values from the table of Student t-test	tcr = 2.093 for P ≤ 0.05 tcr = 2.8609 for P < 0.01	
The correlation is statistically significant at the level	0.05	all

So, it was found, that increasing preparation time for tests evaluation lead to their computer results' deterioration. And the better was their percentage of correct answers – the better student mastered bioorganic chemistry and had higher mark, meaning he understood the solved problems.

Summing up, it was proved that the most important for university bioorganic chemistry successful study was school organic chemistry knowledge and deep understanding of the material.

References:

1. Wilson R. C. Using the Correlation Tool from the Excel 2007 and Excel 2010 Analysis ToolPak. [Электронный ресурс] – Режим доступа. – URL: <http://hubpages.com/hub/Using-the-Correlation-Tool-from-the-Excel-2007-and-Excel-2010-Analysis-ToolPak>.
2. Расчет коэффициента ранговой корреляции Спирмена [Электронный ресурс] – Режим доступа. – URL: http://www.spearman.ru/ru/correlation_analysis/spearman_rank_correlation_coefficient/calc.
3. KS-test Data Entry [Электронный ресурс] – Режим доступа. – URL: http://www.physics.csbsju.edu/stats/KS-test.n.plot_form.html